

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
California State University, Los Angeles

IMPROVING PERCEPTIONS OF MATERNAL RESPECTFUL CARE
AMONG BLACK WOMEN

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Sharilyn Kelly

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Melissa Dyo, PhD, RN, AGNP-C Team Leader
Margaret Brady, PhD, RN, CPNP-PC, Team Member

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Author Note

Sharilyn Kelly - <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4161-1599>
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ABSTRACT

Black women have two to three times the adjusted risk for severe maternal morbidity, with over half of these cases reported as preventable. A lack of respectful maternity care (RMC) may influence this increased risk. RMC is a philosophy that emphasizes the fundamental human rights of birthing women and supports their individual needs and preferences. RMC can help mitigate racial and ethnic outcome disparities by creating psychological safety for the obstetric patient. This quality improvement project aimed to enrich Black women's birthing experience and perceptions of RMC by implementing a patient-centered communication technique based on the 2022 Association of Women's Health, Obstetric, and Neonatal Nurses Respectful Maternity Framework and Evidence-Based Clinical Practice Guideline recommendations. Perinatal nurses completed education modules regarding RMC at an acute care hospital's Birth Care Center in Southern California. Postpartum patients' perceptions of care before and after the intervention were surveyed prior to discharge. The results were stratified by race and ethnicity, showing limited participation by Black postpartum patients. Despite the small number of participants, RMC may have positively impacted Black patients' perception of respectful maternal care. Future studies with larger samples are needed to confirm RMC as an effective strategy to address perceptions of respectful maternal care among Black women. Additional research is necessary to determine if RMC is an intervention that can mitigate the clinical outcome disparities of Black birthing patients feel respected, honored, and heard.

Keywords: perinatal care, African American, Black women, bias, cultural competence, discrimination, obstetric abuse, obstetric racism, nursing, ethnicity, race, culture, respectful maternal care.

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Background

Unrelenting inequities exist in receiving optimal quality perinatal care in the United States. As a result, Black women are at increased risk for adverse birth outcomes, as evidenced by the disparities in maternal morbidity and mortality rates. For example, the likelihood of death for Black women during childbirth is three to four times higher than for White women (Gyamfi-Bannerman et al., 2018; Main et al., 2020). In addition, Black women have two to three times the adjusted risk for severe maternal morbidity (SMM; Lyndon, 2019). Eight medical categories comprise SMM and include obstetric hemorrhage, hypertension disorders of pregnancy, maternal sepsis, and cardiac complications. More than half of the SMM cases are preventable and may be influenced by the lack of respectful maternity care (RMC) provided during delivery (Altman et al., 2020). RMC is a philosophy that emphasizes the basic human rights of birthing women, their newborns, and families and supports their individual needs and preferences (Shakibazadeh et al., 2017).

Problem Statement

Research studies have revealed disturbing findings wherein large percentages of physicians, midwives, and nurses have experienced situations where patients were put at risk due to a care team member's failure to listen or lack of response to the patient's expressions of concern (Vedam et al., 2017). Patients have a desire for meaningful connections with their providers during maternity care. Still, they often find themselves talked over, disrespected, discriminated against, and coerced to have interventions they did not want (Lyndon, 2019). Therefore, providers must spend quality time with their patients to nurture a relationship based on mutual respect, empathy, and kindness.

RMC is necessary to improve women's trust and confidence in their care providers and make them feel heard when voicing their care concerns or desires based on their lived experiences (Moridi et al., 2020). In addition, RMC can help mitigate racial and ethnic disparities by creating psychological safety for the obstetric patient to speak up, voice her concerns, and be heard, especially if a member of a marginalized population. Finally, while complications in pregnancy and childbirth are not always preventable, the timely recognition and appropriate response to changes in the patient's condition can mitigate the progression from unexpected complications to severe morbidity and death (Lyndon, 2019). Mutual respect expressed through listening to and believing patients' or families' concerns can facilitate the timely clinical interventions necessary to achieve optimal perinatal care and decrease maternal outcome disparities (Bohren et al., 2020).

Purpose Statement

The overarching goal of this project is to improve Black mothers' perception of the RMC they received in the project setting. Therefore, the purpose of this DNP project was twofold: (1) to develop, implement, and evaluate an educational program for perinatal nurses that teaches patient-centered communication to enable the nurse to connect with the patient and provide respectful maternal care and (2) to evaluate the effect of the program on Black women's perspectives of RMC.

Supporting Framework

Practice-based frameworks in clinical projects serve as guidelines to translate theory into practice. A framework helps to provide a strong foundation and defines a project's boundaries to help shape a project's purpose, methods, and outcomes (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The Iowa Model (2015) guided this DNP project. Developed by clinical leaders with expertise in research

utilization, the Iowa Model was published in 1994 as a derivative of the Quality Assurance Model Using Research and Diffusion of Innovations Theory (Hanrahan et al., 2019). It was initially implemented at the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics (UIHC) to guide the health care providers to improve patient care by implementing research findings. It has since been used to implement EBP in various care settings (Titler et al., 2001). This exploratory model has stood the test of time and has evolved to reflect the valuable feedback for improvement from 600 users representing 130 countries (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The most recent iteration of the Iowa Model was made available in 2015 (Appendix A, Figure 1). It included the patient and family values and preferences as part of its systematic approach to determine the impact of EBP on patient outcomes (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017).

There are many barriers to implementing EBP. The Institute of Medicine estimates it takes greater than seventeen years to translate research findings into clinical practice. Unfortunately, while nurses value EBP to inform their daily practice, they need education, access to data, and time to implement EBP in their clinical reality (Brown, 2014). However, implementing evidence becomes more attainable using a structured approach and process like the ones built in the Iowa model. The literature is rich with examples where the Iowa Model improved nurses' aptitude to implement EBP successfully. For example, a team of intensive care nurses at a hospital in Malawi employed the Iowa Model to guide their process of finding a potential practice change through clinical problem identification, literature review, and the eventual adoption of an evidence-based intervention for fever control (Chiwaula et al., 2021). Similarly, a group of oncology nurses used the Iowa Model to guide their fall prevention efforts. It guided them effectively through the seven steps of the process to organize a practice change that reduced patient falls (Brown, 2014).

Identifying triggering issues or opportunities is the first step in the Iowa Model. For example, clinical findings or patient issues, organizational, state, or national quality initiatives, review of organizational data or introduction of new evidence, regulatory requirements, or changes in the philosophy of care are all opportunities for identifying triggers or introducing improvements. Once an opportunity is identified, the next step is to construct the question or purpose statement using the PICOT format to address the (P) population of interest, (I) intervention, (C) comparison intervention or group, (O) outcome, and (T) time (Melnik et al., 2010). Correctly stating the project's purpose or posing the question enables a team to have a more focused strategy to review the literature effectively and scope the evidence to determine its relevance (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The evidence informs the action to be taken in the decisional point, built in the Iowa Model. This forced decisional point ensures that a team determines if a proposed project is a priority for the organization or care setting. Proposed projects associated with a higher return on investments, or the most significant risk exposure reduction, will likely have higher priority. Organizational support at all levels is critical to the success of an EBP project to ensure resources are available to advance a project. The model prompts considering a different issue if the identified problem is not aligned with the organizational or care-setting priorities (Brown, 2014).

If it is determined that an improvement opportunity is a priority, the next step in the Iowa model is to form a project team. Identifying stakeholders and subject matter experts is essential in selecting team members. Attention should be paid to creating an interdisciplinary team to include all areas impacted by the project (Buckwalter et al., 2017). Once the group is formed, the members will gather and critique the relevant research related to the PICOT statement or question and weigh the evidence's quality, quantity, consistency, and risk-benefit ratio (Brown,

2014). In addition, to synthesize the research findings into clear and consistent information, it is beneficial to organize the selected articles by categories and themes on a summary table (Titler et al., 2001).

The next decision point in the Iowa model algorithm involves determining if sufficient evidence exists to implement a practice change relevant to the identified problem. If the collated evidence is deemed insufficient, the model guides the team onto a separate path to conduct a research study. However, the team moves to the next step if the collated evidence is deemed sufficient. The next step focuses on designing and piloting the proposed intervention or change in practice (Brown, 2014). To develop and trial the proposed practice change, the team should engage patients and families to understand and validate their preferences, identify required resources, and address any limitations and necessary approvals to incorporate into the intervention design and pilot implementation protocol. Next, evaluation criteria are developed, and baseline data are collected. Finally, an implementation plan is developed, providers are prepared, and project collateral is produced (Buckwalter et al., 2017).

After pilot implementation, data are collected and reported. The third decision point in the Iowa Model requires the team to determine if the change is appropriate for adoption in practice. Evaluating the pilot data helps with this decision to move forward with the improvement project. If the results do not support the change, the team must revisit the pilot design and perform a plan, do, study, and act (PDSA) cycle to consider other interventions or strategies. On the other hand, if the implementation plan is effective and other areas may also benefit from the intervention, the next step is integrating and sustaining the evidence-based practice change (Buckwalter et al., 2017). Identifying and including key stakeholders to incorporate the change throughout the care setting is critical for integrating and hardwiring

change into the system. Another vital element to promoting the sustainment of EBP is identifying and monitoring metrics for processes and outcomes, including balancing measures. These metrics should reveal if deviations in practice are occurring so the protocol can be re-infused where and when needed (Buckwalter et al., 2017). The last step in the model is to disseminate the findings. A shared governance structure can be used to communicate results to clinicians within the healthcare setting.

Application of the Iowa Model

In this DNP project, step one was triggered when inequities in the birth outcomes for Black women were identified by a state collaborative seeking participation from hospitals serving diverse populations to participate in a pilot initiative to improve Birth Equity. The project facility participated in this pilot collaborative with four other hospitals and community stakeholders to review the outcome data collected and develop a toolkit to improve birth outcomes for Black birthing women.

To fit in the context of the facility where this project took place, a specific purpose was formulated; this DNP project aimed to improve the perception of respectful maternal care by introducing a patient-centered communication technique to assist the nursing team at the facility in delivering respectful maternal care and to ensure all women could be active participants in their reproductive care.

The IOWA model algorithm has a decisional point to determine if this issue is a priority. The Health Care System in which the project took place had added diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) to its fiscal year 2022 and fiscal year 2023 strategic plan in response to national events, which provided evidence of persistent structural racism and a demand for action. The project site data demonstrated a significant and consistent racial and ethnic gap in the SMM

rates. For example, in 2021, the SMM rate for non-Hispanic Black patients was 4% compared to 2.8% for all other races and ethnicities. The nursing staff's adoption of the RMC behaviors allowed them to begin to close this gap by ensuring all patients were heard, seen, and respected while receiving optimal care based on their individual needs. Therefore, this DNP project was a health system priority and was well-aligned with the organizational goal of addressing racial and ethnic disparities for patients and employees at all levels.

The third step in the model is to form a team. A Birth Equity Committee was established to work with the state collaborative team. The local facility team consisted of the author, who is the Interim Chief Nursing Officer of the project facility and the Executive Director of Perinatal Services, the Program Director of the outpatient OB/GYN clinic, the Clinical Operations Director for the Labor & Delivery Unit, the Clinical Operations Director for the Postpartum Unit, the Clinical Operations Director for the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit, three Perinatal Educators, the Perinatal Safety Nurse, the Quality Manager, the Program Director of Perinatal Palliative Care, the Spiritual Care Chaplain, the Perinatal Risk Manager, the Medical Director of Maternal-Fetal Medicine, the Obstetric Chief of Staff, and several patient-facing perinatal team members as well as a patient advisor. This team evaluated the existing literature to inform the development of the intervention. The composition of this team changed as the project progressed, and the need for additional resources was identified. A team representative from the project facility's Human Resources department was added to provide additional guidance and input from their knowledge and perspective.

The next decision point was to determine if sufficient evidence existed that supported the proposed intervention. Based on the literature review performed by the author and then by the Birth Equity Committee, ample evidence supported educating the care team in the behaviors that

convey respectful maternity care. A table of evidence was constructed to categorize and assess the level of evidence for each article selected. The evidence, including retrieval, organization, critique, and synthesis, is presented in the literature section of this paper.

The model's next step is to design and pilot the practice change. The first action in this project design was to collect baseline data before implementing the intervention by requesting all postpartum patients in the Postpartum Care Unit (PPCU) and the Perinatal Special Care Unit (PSCU) to complete patient experience surveys to assess the level of respect experienced during their pregnancy and birth. The intervention objectives were guided by the Respectful Maternity Care Framework and Evidence-based clinical practice guidelines by the Association of Women's Health and Neonatal Nurses (Appendix B, Figure 1). Next, the project team developed an implementation and evaluation plan. Once completed, the project team presented the project and intervention training to the BirthCare Center (BCC) nursing leadership team. The leadership team participated in a debriefing session with the project team to provide feedback regarding the training and materials. Finally, the project team made revisions based on the feedback and prepared to promote the RMC training throughout the Perinatal service line.

This DNP project evaluated the efficacy of the RMC training of the Registered Nurses to improve the Black Postpartum patients' perception of the level of respect experienced during their delivery and postpartum hospital stay.

Review of Literature

Overview

A literature search was conducted for all English-language, peer-reviewed studies to inform the following categories: racial disparities and birth outcomes; obstetric abuse and racism, perspectives and voices of the women of color; healthcare provider behaviors; and respectful maternal care. Databases searched to find evidence include CINAHL, PubMed, and EBSCO. Terms used to search included: "perinatal care," "African American or Black women," "bias," "cultural competence," "discrimination," "obstetric abuse and racism," "nursing," "ethnicity or race or culture," and "respectful maternal care." To ensure the most relevant research was used to guide the DNP project's development, the electronic database search was refined to include only those published between 2017 and the present. These searches yielded a total of 33 articles. In addition, to focus on the intrapartum experiences and opportunities for improvement, additional exclusion criteria included unintended pregnancy, the risk for preterm birth, and breastfeeding complications. This further reduced the search results to 20 articles in total.

Racial Disparities and Birth Outcomes

Non-Hispanic Black women die from pregnancy-related causes at four times the rate of non-Hispanic White women, and their risk for severe maternal morbidity (SMM) is twice that of White women. These rates cannot be explained by socioeconomic factors alone. More than one-half of these cases of SMM are preventable and may be sensitive to the quality of care provided during birth (Burriss et al., 2021; Gyamfi-Bannerman et al., 2018; Howell, 2018; Lister et al., 2019; Main et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020). In addition, Black women experience higher mortality from hemorrhage, hypertensive disorders of pregnancy, and cardiomyopathy. Black

women also experience a higher rate of SMM, which occurs 50-100 times more frequently than maternal death and includes major complications in childbirth, such as pulmonary edema, renal failure, disseminated intravascular coagulation, hysterectomy, and transfusion. Furthermore, Black women are more likely to be readmitted during the postpartum period due to complications and suffer life-threatening SMM during their readmission (Aziz et al., 2019; Howell, 2018 Howell & Zeitlin, 2017; Main et al., 2020).

Obstetric Abuse and Racism

Obstetric racism is the contemporary manifestation of ideologies, practices, and exploitations of reproduction in Black women resulting in social and clinical neglect. Obstetric abuse and racism threaten positive birth outcomes and experiences in hospital settings among Black birthing women. Obstetric patients may be subjected to acts of violence because they are in a vulnerable, reliant state. Abuse can occur when providers take advantage of an obstetric patient's state and exert dominance to inflict dehumanizing treatment, including being ignored, belittled, or verbally humiliated by healthcare providers (Davis, 2019; Davis, 2020; Julian et al., 2020; Vedam et al., 2019). Studies have revealed that Black women have a higher incidence of abuse due to obstetric racism. Presumed incompetence, mistreatment, disrespect, interventions without explanation or consent, and painful procedures without medication are examples of obstetric racism in maternal care (Davis, 2019; Davis, 2020; Julian et al., 2020; Vedam et al., 2019;). Structural racism exists when systemic regulations and processes differentiate access to goods and services based on individual ethnic group membership. Structural racism can inhibit medical professionals from listening to their patients and can hold a pregnant woman solely responsible for the poor outcome of her newborn (Scott et al., 2019).

Perspectives and Voices of Black Women

Black women have reported negative experiences with hospital births. Those experiences include having interventions forced upon them and being separated from their babies without explanation (Davis, 2019). Like most women, Black women desire complete, truthful, and comprehensive information regarding their care and available options. Unfortunately, many feel that information is withheld or "packaged" dependent upon the action or outcome the provider desires to control and influence or manipulate the patient's decision-making. The provider's "packaging" of information is often based on biases and stereotypes due to a lack of knowledge of the patient as an individual (Altman et al., 2019). Unless a Black woman presents to her provider with presumable racialized health factors such as having a hypertension disorder or diabetes, their provider may not take any self-reported concerns about her pregnancy seriously and deem her as having no or low risk without further clinical exploration. The provider's failure to appreciate and address the patient's fears reveals how structurally embedded racism prevents medical professionals from hearing their patient, potentially resulting in harm to her or her fetus (Davis, 2019). Women want a provider who will take the time to get to know them as an individual by asking questions and providing information to make them feel comfortable and safe with their pregnancy. After a medical visit, they want to feel confident they were heard and cared for rather than just being checked. These positive experiences were mostly reported in the context of a well-established relationship with a provider or practice who knew the patient. A consistent provider allows for establishing an ongoing relationship to increase trust and familiarity (Altman et al., 2020; Altman et al., 2019; Lister et al., 2019; Roman et al., 2017).

Concerning their maternal morbidity, Black women described their childbirth complication as a "distressing" or "traumatic" experience (Wang et al., 2020). Many reported

pain, shock, and extended suffering following the event. In addition, many women did not feel heard when expressing pain levels, physical symptoms, and therapeutic preferences, leaving them feeling ignored, isolated, and powerless. Reports of violations of their dignity, privacy, and confidentiality were widespread. The most frequent mistreatment was being shouted at or scolded by a healthcare provider, followed by being ignored. Violation of physical privacy and healthcare providers threatening to withhold or impose unwanted treatment were also reported (Vedam et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2020).

Healthcare Provider Behaviors

The inability to prevent death from healthcare complications has been called "failure to rescue" (Lyndon, 2019). Communication breakdowns, disrespect, questionable workloads, and fear of embarrassment contributed to a hospital's failure to rescue rate through delayed recognition of changes in patient condition and delayed care escalation. Black women are more likely than White women to experience poor communication during perinatal health provider encounters. The use of stereotypes by healthcare providers and patient views of these stereotypes affects the experience of care quality for those in marginalized groups (Roman et al., 2017). This contributes to the communication breakdown and lack of confidence between the patient and provider. Good listening skills, appropriate responses to a patient's or colleague's concerns or critical feedback, and identifying and addressing any implicit biases are all strategies to overcome communication breakdown and enhance clinician communication with the patient (Lyndon, 2019). In addition, these skills are vital competencies needed during a severe obstetric complication to ensure an equitable response to all changes in the patient's condition to mitigate any poor outcomes or emotional trauma. Green et al. (2021), Lyndon (2019), and Wang et al. (2020) postulated that improving communication to ensure that women feel heard and informed

throughout obstetrical care could decrease disparities in perinatal care quality and enhance the patient experience for all women.

Respectful Maternity Care

RMC preserves the patient's dignity, privacy, and confidentiality. It also protects the patient from harm and mistreatment and provides informed consent, shared decision-making, and continuous support during the intrapartum and postpartum periods. Women receiving respectful maternity care are less likely to report mistreatment and abuse (Bohren et al., 2020). To provide respectful maternity care to all women, the healthcare systems must have structures and processes that support and respect caregivers and create a therapeutic environment for care delivery for both the care providers and the women. Laboring women want kindness, respect, inclusion, and safety. In 2018, the World Health Organization (WHO) published recommendations for intrapartum care for a positive childbirth experience. These recommendations called out the need for non-clinical intrapartum practices such as providing emotional support through labor companionship, effective communication, and respectful care. Even though affordable to implement, they had not been considered priorities in many birth settings. Adherence to the WHO clinical guidelines can help provide evidenced-based respectful maternity care, especially in lower-resource contexts (Bohren et al., 2020; Morlidl et al., 2020; Shakibazadeh et al., 2018).

Summary

In summary, the literature review revealed that to overcome the long history of obstetrical abuse and racism, all perinatal care providers should be educated in and adopt the care paradigm of RMC to mitigate the preventable threats to maternal mortality and morbidity. The mistreatment and disrespect of Black women in the perinatal arena must be eradicated to prevent

outcome disparities and build trust between the patients and providers. Themes from the literature review that will be integrated into this project include the awareness and understanding of obstetrical abuse and racism, the desire for Black women to be heard, seen, and respected during their obstetrical care, and the need for providers to adopt patient-centered communication techniques to display respect, care, and understanding of the patient's needs throughout their perinatal hospital stay.

Methods

Design

This DNP project was a quality improvement (QI) initiative aimed to enrich Black Women's birth experience to increase perceptions of respectful care by implementing clinical practice guideline recommendations. This was an appropriate approach, as the primary goal of quality improvement is to address a clinical issue to solve a problem or improve care (Bonnell & Smith, 2017). Baseline and post-implementation data were collected to measure the impact on Black women's perceptions of having received respectful maternal care by a team of Perinatal nurses who participated in an education program that focused on patient-centered communication techniques during labor, delivery, and postpartum care.

Setting

This QI project occurred in the BCC in a Southern California acute care hospital. The BCC is comprised of 21 private labor, delivery, and recovery (LDR) rooms, 11 private perinatal special care unit (PSCU) rooms, and 56 private postpartum care unit (PPCU) rooms. This maternity program averages 5,800 deliveries annually and serves a diverse population. In 2022, the BCC patient demographics reflected 43.3% Hispanic US-born; 17.3% Hispanic non-US born; 12.8% White; 10.6% Black; 9.2% Asian; 0.9% Pacific Islander; 0.2% Native American; 3.9% Multiracial; and 1.7% other/unknown. Approximately 350 perinatal nursing staff provide these patients bedside antepartum, intrapartum, and postpartum care.

Participants

Each patient admitted for intrapartum care and transferred to the PPCU or the PSCU was invited to participate in the patient experience survey before discharge to determine their perceptions of equitable and respectful care. Participation in the survey was voluntary. All nurses

employed by the project site and providing perinatal patient care were required to participate by completing the RMC education module. This included all full-time, part-time, per diem, and contracted nurses. The nurses were considered to have completed the module upon passing the seven-question multiple-choice post-test with a minimum score of 80 points out of 100 possible. They were also expected to complete their commitment statement and integrate their commitment to RMC into their practice by demonstrating the RMC behaviors upon completing the RMC module.

Stakeholders

There was an impact on several groups and individuals executing this study. The perinatal nursing teams and leadership for LDR, PSCU, and PPCU were involved in the intervention planning and implementation phases. All nursing team members received training to integrate a patient-centered communication technique into their practice and were observed for compliance by their leaders. The Nurse Executive Council approved a RMC Champion role at the project facility as an element of the professional advancement program if the nurse champion chooses to pursue clinical promotion. Nine RMC nurse champions were identified by their unit leaders based on their employment status, interest in the project, and their eligibility and desire to pursue clinical advancement. The RMC Champions assisted staff with implementing the communication technique and executing their RMC commitment statement. They also role-modeled the ideal behaviors that demonstrated RMC to the intrapartum and postpartum patients.

Ethical Considerations

This DNP project was submitted to the site's Institutional Review Board (IRB) and was deemed exempt from review (Appendix C). The hospital's Chief Nurse Executive permitted this project to be conducted at the site (Appendix D). This project was also submitted to and

approved by the IRB at California State University, Long Beach (Appendix E). A subsequent IRB revision request was completed to add the response data to a question from an additional patient survey source (Appendix F).

The survey instrument used for this project was developed using the fully Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) compliant Qualtrics tool. The database coordinator granted permission to use the survey results for this project (Appendix G). To address the possibility that participants could experience discomfort or emotional distress if recalling a bad birthing experience due to perinatal loss, birth trauma, obstetric abuse, or obstetric racism, resource links were provided on the informed consent for the participant to access emotional support if distress was triggered (Appendix H). This survey was constructed without capturing patient-identifying data and with an option to restrict to only those with the anonymous link. The anonymized responses were viewable to only those with permission, including the project sites' Birth Equity team members and the data analyst at Stanford University. In addition, Internet protocol tracking was turned off in Qualtrics to further reduce obtaining identifiable data. Data collected were retained on a password-protected work computer.

Surveys, Metrics, and Data Collection

The Patient Reported Experience Measures (PREM) survey was developed during the California Maternal Quality Care Collaborative (CMQCC) Birth Equity Collaborative pilot, of which the project facility is a member. The collaborative aim was to create a short patient-reported experience survey to inform birth equity quality improvement opportunities. The Birth Equity collaborative members reviewed questions from the Mothers Autonomy in Decision Making scale (MADM) and the Mothers on Respect index (MOR). The MADM scale and the

MOR are reliable and valid tools that assess the level of support and autonomy a person feels when participating in decision-making discussions with an obstetric provider, as Vedam et al. (2017) reported. The team chose 12 of the questions reviewed to be included in the PREM survey based on the questions' perceived ability to elicit information regarding women's perceptions of the respectful care they received during their birth experience, before and after the implementation of the Respectful Maternal Care intervention (Appendix I).

In addition to the 12 questions, the PREM survey included demographic data, including race, ethnicity, age range, and whether this is her first birth. The next part of the survey focused on the hospital experience asking the participant to respond to statements about their perceptions of their treatment during their birthing experience. Each of these statements required a five-point Likert scale response. The next section of the survey asked the participant to reflect on the hospital birthing experience and indicate their agreement with specific statements regarding the care team. Again, each of these statements required a Likert scale answer. The last section asked for any comments about any experience during childbirth that they wanted to share.

The birth certificate clerks provided information regarding the opportunity to participate in the survey when visiting patients to complete and verify their birth certificate information. With the use of a standard script to mitigate any perceptions of coercion or intimidation to participate, the birth clerks offered the PREM flyer with the QR code for the patients to scan with their smartphones or offered a hospital device to scan and complete the survey (Appendix J). In addition, PREM survey flyers were posted in each PPCU and PSCU room to encourage patient participation. The patients opting to participate used their smartphones or a hospital-provided device to scan the PREM survey flyer's quick response (QR) code, providing the informed consent and survey link. The PREM survey database is managed by Stanford

University, which produces a monthly report that stratifies the survey results by race and ethnicity for the project site as part of the ongoing Birth Equity collaborative work with CMQCC.

Another data source used to evaluate the patient perspective of care was the Hospital Consumer Assessment of Healthcare Providers and Systems (HCAHPS) scores for the project facility. The HCAHPS is an Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ) patient satisfaction survey instrument used nationally to help organizations use their results to improve the quality of their care. This survey is routinely sent to all patients post-discharge from the project site's PPCU or PSCU. Baseline and post-implementation data were collected regarding the patients' responses to the question, "How often did nurses treat you with courtesy and respect." This question was added because it aligned well with the PREM survey and specifically addressed nursing care perceptions versus physicians or other hospital staff (Appendix K). The HCAHPS reports are received monthly and analyzed by the project site's Quality Department. This project spanned from March to the end of December 2022 (Appendix L).

Educational Intervention, Procedures, and Outcomes

The educational intervention for this project was based on recommendations from the 2022 Association of Women's Health, Obstetric and Neonatal Nurses (AWHONN) Respectful Maternity Care Framework and the Evidence-Based Clinical Practice Guideline. Awareness, acceptance, mutual respect, and shared decision-making are the four categories under which AWHONN provides specific evidence-based recommendations to improve respectful care for pregnant women. This DNP project focused on the mutual respect component of these guidelines. *Mutual respect* is defined as a shared process in which two or more persons or groups hold each other in regard by demonstrating care, concern, or compassion for the other's needs or

feelings (AWHONN, 2022). The recommendations included using a patient-centered communication technique to promote active listening for the nurse to acknowledge and honor patient wishes to the best of their ability while avoiding minimizing or discounting any patient concerns or needs.

The AWHONN RMC Commitment Form was adapted for this project to facilitate the patient-centered communication technique intervention (Appendix M). The nursing membership of the Birth Equity team reviewed a recent study by Golden et al. (2022) regarding patient perceptions of provider communication demonstrated that patients perceive better overall communication with their caregivers when they sit at the bedside. Therefore, the team members endorsed the AWHONN RMC Care Commitment form to include expectations for the nurses to incorporate the practice of sitting with patients to demonstrate the recommended RMC behaviors while focusing on their patient's needs, concerns, and wishes for their childbirth and postpartum experiences.

A PowerPoint presentation was developed by the author based on the AWHONN RMC Clinical Practice Guidelines to educate the Perinatal nursing staff regarding the disparities in patient outcomes by race and ethnicity, the history of obstetrical abuse and racism, the behaviors associated with RMC, and why this intervention is critical in mitigating these gaps in care. A seven-question post-test was included to assess understanding of the concepts and expectations. The project site employs three master's degree-prepared experienced Perinatal Educators who were also members of the Birth Equity team. After their review and endorsement of the education material, the PowerPoint presentation was uploaded to the project facilities learning management system (LMS) as a required self-directed education module assigned to all BCC

nurses beginning on July 17th, 2022, through December 31st, 2022. The completion rates of this module were tracked as a weekly process measure over three months.

The Nine RMC champions were comprised of five nurses from LDR and four from the PPCU. The RMC champions were oriented to their roles in October 2022 and provided with all needed supplies for engaging with and educating the nursing staff (Appendix N). The RMC champions facilitated individual and small-group training within each unit. As each nursing team member was trained, the RMC champion asked them to sign the AWHONN RMC Commitment Form, which committed them to perform a set of behaviors to demonstrate RMC to their patients and allowed them to commit to focusing on at least one of the five specific aspects of RMC to integrate into their practice. The five focused commitments included behaviors to exhibit treating the patient with dignity and respect; providing the patient with evidenced-based care; listening and believing the patient; assisting the patient with shared decision-making; and being the patient's advocate. Each nurse chose and signed a commitment card to post on an RMC commitment banner displayed in each unit. They were also given a corresponding button to wear to express their commitment to their patients.

The performance of this communication technique was a process measure reported by each patient surveyed by unit leadership. The leaders asked each patient they encountered during their daily rounds if their nurse had sat with them today to discuss their goals for their birth or postpartum experience. The results of the leader surveys were posted on each unit's established Managing for Daily Improvements (MDI) board. MDI boards were implemented in the project facility's patient care units in 2020 to engage the staff in identifying issues in patient safety, experience, and progression. Incremental overtime was measured to ensure the new practice would not add additional time to the nurse's shift.

Data Analysis

The education and training plan's progress was tracked by the LMS module completion rate and compliance with the communication technique on all units from July/August through October 2022. These unit process measures were monitored and tracked through the MDI board process, displaying a run chart with the number of patients reporting the communication intervention that occurred. If 90% of the patients interviewed reported experiencing the intervention during that shift, a green dot was displayed on the calendar date. If the communication intervention goal of 90% was not met, a red dot was placed on the calendar. The reasons why were entered and tracked on a Pareto chart to make trends visible regarding any obstacles to success for problem-solving. The data collected on the Pareto charts were reviewed weekly by the BCC unit's leadership team to discern the most significant barriers to integrating this intervention into the nurses' practice. The unit care team then worked collaboratively through daily huddles to problem-solve and experiment until they saw sustained improvement in compliance with the intervention.

Incremental double-time was monitored after the implementation of the communication technique. The intent was to identify any significant impact on the nurses' time management and ability to leave the shift on time. Any incurred double-time demonstrates a late clock-out, possibly due to the new practice.

Pre- and post-intervention data about the patient perceptions were collected through PREM and HCAHPS surveys which measured aspects of respectful maternal care with 5-point Likert scale questions ranging from 1 = never/strongly disagree to 5 = always/strongly agree, including a middle neutral option. Mean scores above the midpoint of 2.5 reflect more favorable perceptions, whereas those below 2.5 indicate less favorable perceptions. The scores were

aggregated monthly onto an Excel spreadsheet and stratified by self-identified race/ethnicity to extract only the responses from the Black women. The total number of deliveries and the number of Black women delivering at the project site were included for each data collection period to determine the PREM and HCAHPS response rates for each population. Descriptive statistics were used to describe the findings. Baseline and post-implementation information was organized into bar charts by question to determine if there was an improvement.

Results

Process Measures

The RMC online module was assigned to a total of 320 registered nurses working within the BCC service line. The completion rate of these 320 nurses was measured from mid-July through December 2022. The goal set by the Birth Equity team was to achieve a minimum completion rate of 80%. By the end of December, 93.75% of the assigned nurses had completed the education module (Appendix O, Figure 1). In addition, 63% of the BCC nursing staff signed and displayed their RMC commitment.

The second process measure was to capture the intervention compliance rate from August through October 2022. The Birth Equity team set a target to achieve a 90% weekly compliance rate. By the end of October, a weekly compliance rate of 93.45% was accomplished (Appendix O, Figure 2).

Balancing Measure

The BCC nurses' double-time was measured pre-implementation of the intervention. From March to July 2022, 1,186 hours of double-time were incurred. After the intervention was implemented, 1,236 hours of double-time was noted, resulting in a net increase of 50 hours.

Outcome Measures

Baseline data were collected from March through July 2022. The total number of deliveries for the pre-intervention period was 2356; 236 (10%) were attributed to Black women. There were 278 responses to the HCAHPS question regarding "respect and courtesy," representing 11.8% of the patients delivered during that time. Of those respondents, 17 identified as Black women (6.1%), representing 7.2% of the total deliveries to Black women. Of those

Black women, 70.5% answered "Always" to the "respect and courtesy" question before implementing the intervention.

The PREM survey yielded 56 respondents representing 2.3% of the total deliveries and five (9%) participants identified as Black women representing 2% of the Black births. The 12-item survey was reduced to nine questions due to the survey's data analyst's inability to stratify three questions by race and ethnicity during the pre-and post-intervention periods. The results of the remaining nine questions were stratified by race, and all responses from participants identifying as Black were extracted. The percentage of Black women responding "Always" or "Strongly Agree" ranged from 60% to 80%.

The same data were collected from participants who delivered their newborns post-intervention implementation from August through December 2022. During this time, there were 2505 deliveries; 272 (10.8%) were attributed to Black women. There were 267 participants who answered the HCAHPS question regarding "respect and courtesy," representing 10.6% of the patients delivered. 13 out of the 267 respondents identified as Black women (4.9%), representing 4.8% of the total deliveries to Black women. Seventy-seven percent of the Black women responded "Always" to the post-intervention question (Appendix P, Figure 1).

The PREM survey generated 82 respondents representing 3.2% of the total deliveries, and 11 (13%) participants identified as Black women representing 4% of the Black births. Again, the results of the nine survey questions were stratified by race, and all responses from participants identifying as Black were extracted. The percentage of Black women responding "Always" or "Strongly Agree" ranged from 71%-91% (Appendix P, Figure 2).

Discussion

This project aimed to improve Black mothers' perception of the respectful maternity care they received at the project site by implementing a patient-centered communication technique. The intention was to provide a tool to enable the perinatal nurse to connect with the patient and provide respectful maternal care by demonstrating associated behaviors.

Process Measures

Completion of the RMC module was monitored along with the intervention compliance rates to determine if the compliance rate would increase as the RMC module completion rate increased. The compliance rate was monitored over 12 weeks starting August 1st and provided a representation of integrating the RMC behaviors into the nursing team's practice. As expected, the intervention compliance rate did increase over time as more nurses completed the RMC module reaching a 93% compliance rate by the end of the monitoring period. The BCC leadership has endorsed adding the intervention compliance question into their leadership rounding to sustain the practice. The nursing team's integration of the communication intervention was designed to increase mutual respect and connection between the nurse and the obstetric patient. The intervention was based on a study by Scott et al. (2019) that demonstrated how learning effective communication skills can mitigate the effects of structural racism that have hindered perinatal providers from listening to their patients.

Balancing Measure

The BCC nurses' double-time increased by 50 hours after implementing the intervention. The baseline double-time hours per delivery was 0.5 hours (1,186 hours/2356 deliveries). Post-intervention double-time hours per delivery was 0.49 hours (1,236 hours/2505 deliveries). Monitoring the BCC nurses' double-time as a balancing measure demonstrated that adding the

intervention did not result in additional double-time despite an additional 149 deliveries during the post-intervention period.

Outcome Measures

Despite the small number of participants, RMC behaviors positively impacted our Black birthing patients' perception of respectful maternal care. The HCAHPS question regarding the nurses providing care with courtesy and respect increased from 70.5% to 77% of Black patients responding "Always." The percentage of Black women responding to the PREM survey questions with "Always" and "Strongly Agree" also increased for eight of the nine items ranging from 2%-22%. These results were anticipated due to the focus on effective communication in relationship-building with the patient, which created an opportunity to increase trust, connection, and mutual respect. Sitting with the patient to engage without distractions and asking open-ended and clarifying questions while displaying empathy will increase the likelihood of detecting challenges and difficulties the patient may be experiencing. Active listening skills that seek to understand the meaning and intent behind words, appropriate actions taken in response to a patient's concerns or comments, and mitigation of any identified implicit biases are all tactics to lessen communication breakdown and optimize the provider and patient connection (Lyndon, 2019). The project site will continue to strive to provide the necessary perinatal nurse staffing to optimize the time and space needed for relationship building between the care providers and their patients. Improved communication to ensure women feel heard and informed during their perinatal care may lead to decreased disparities in outcomes and an enriched birth experience (Green et al., 2021; Lyndon, 2019; Wang et al., 2020).

Implications for Practice

Since the inception of this project, additional programs and resources have been developed to address the need to deliver respectful care. In October 2022, the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ) disseminated its evidence-based practice systematic review protocol for Respectful Maternity Care. This review aims to study each component of RMC to determine validated measures and synthesize strategies to provide RMC. These details will inform maternal safety bundle revisions, clinical practice leaders, and policymakers (AHRQ, 2022). In addition, the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) launched its "Hear Her" campaign on November 17, 2022. This campaign seeks to improve communication between obstetric patients, families, and their perinatal providers to build trust and engage them in their care to reduce maternal morbidity and improve clinical outcomes – e.g., listening to patient concerns because a woman knows her body best and knows when something does not feel normal (CDC, 2022). The CDC Hear Her campaign website has many resources and tools for patients, families, and healthcare professionals.

As researchers study interventions to improve the outcome disparities for Black women and their newborns, the connection between the patient and the caregiver must be considered. The patients' capacity to trust and build a genuine rapport with their nurses may depend on the nurse's ability to communicate and connect with the patient in a meaningful way. Nurses are in the optimal position to help Black women feel respected and heard by honoring their desires and addressing their concerns during their childbirth experience. Integrating the practice of sitting with the patient to discuss their goals, wishes, and concerns for their birth experience gives the nurse insight into what the patient may have experienced in her life and what she needs to ensure a physically and psychologically safe delivery for her and her infant. The opportunity to amplify

the patient's voice and act as her advocate is essential to changing Black women's perception of systemic racism and obstetric abuse in healthcare.

Nurses' adoption of RMC behaviors is imperative. Intentional integration of practices to promote dignity, shared decision-making, evidence-based care, and listening to understand how to respond appropriately to advocate for patients' needs will result in improved healthcare experiences and perceptions of respect. The findings of this project (i.e., improved perceptions of RMC by Black birthing patients) demonstrated emerging benefits from the perinatal staff training in RMC communication. The practice of these behaviors to demonstrate respectful care should be considered in all healthcare venues, not only perinatal care settings.

The project site will continue implementing all care recommendations provided in the AWHONN RMC framework and guidelines resource. The site has partnered with AWHONN for phase 2 of their national RMC implementation project and is also looking at using a patient mobile application to gather additional data from their Black patients regarding their patient care experiences. Patient experience scores stratified by race and ethnicity will continue to be reviewed to evaluate the implemented interventions' impact on all groups. Lister et al. (2019) hypothesized that treating Black women with respect and compassion, while providing continuity of care, may ultimately result in improved perinatal outcomes and reduced maternal mortality through their improved engagement with the healthcare system. To study this potential effect, SMM rates by race and ethnicity will be added to the measures to detect any improvements in clinical outcomes during this next project phase. A nurse satisfaction assessment will also be added to determine if the nurse feels improved job satisfaction and engagement after integrating the RMC behaviors into practice.

Strengths

The strength of this project was the engaged nursing staff, and their willingness to self-reflect to attempt to identify any implicit biases they may have had that could inhibit their connection with their Black patients. The project site's work with the CMQCC Birth Equity project had well prepared the nursing team for this project. In addition, the Birth Equity team has engaged with the Hospital Association of Southern California to participate in the *Cherished Futures* collaborative. This collaborative focuses on connecting to one's local Black community to understand better how to improve our BirthCare Center services to improve perinatal outcomes for our Black patients. The site's Birth Equity team has demonstrated an extraordinary commitment to understanding and overcoming biases to deliver outstanding care to all their birthing patients.

Limitations

Several issues arose during this project which resulted in some limitations. First, gaining participants for the PREM survey proved to be complicated. The team did not want to exclude anyone from participation, so it lacked focus on obtaining Black women as participants. As a result, the sample was extremely small once stratified by race and ethnicity to analyze for statistical significance. The project site also experienced a severe staffing shortage during this project. High nurse turnover and short staffing in LDR and PPCU made keeping nurses trained and focused on sustaining the communication technique and promoting survey participation challenging, which may have contributed to the small sample size.

The project site's HCAHPS score response rates were 11.8% during the baseline data collection and 10.6% during the post-intervention collection period. Both response rates are

below the national response rate of 26% of eligible discharged patients. All races and ethnicities are represented in these rates. Additional respondents would increase the strength of the data.

The PREM survey has not undergone validity and reliability testing. Both the MADM and the MOR are validated tools; however, neither was used in their entirety to create the PREM survey. This limits the generalizability of the PREM survey question responses. The use of a validated, reliable tool would have strengthened this study. If used again, tests should be conducted to establish the PREM survey as a reliable and valid instrument for collecting patient data.

Conclusion

This project demonstrates the importance of the nurse and patient connection in providing Black women with psychological safety to communicate their needs and desires during their perinatal care. This is key to improving Black birthing women's perception of respect from their care providers. Due to findings of obstetrical racism and abuse and the gaps in access to equitable care to achieve equitable outcomes (Burriss et al., 2021; Davis, 2019; Howell, 2018; Julian et al., 2020; Lister et al., 2019; Scott et al., 2019; Vedam et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2020), the focus of obstetric care for Black women must be to ensure they feel treated with dignity and as individuals with individual needs. They must be considered the experts of their bodies to effectively partner with their caregivers to achieve their desired birth experience. Additional research is needed to determine if RMC is an intervention that can mitigate the clinical outcome disparities if Black birthing patients feel respected, honored, and heard.

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Appendix A

Permission to use Iowa Model

From: Kimberly Jordan – University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics <survey-bounce@survey.uiowa.edu>

Date: February 25, 2022 at 9:31:27 AM PST

To: [REDACTED]

Subject: Permission to Use The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

Reply-To: Kimberly Jordan – University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics <kimberly-jordan@uiowa.edu>

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Figure 1

The Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

Appendix B

Permission to AWHONN RMC Products

From: permissions <permissions@awhonn.org>
Sent: Thursday, March 10, 2022 6:14 AM
To: Sharilyn Kelly <SKelly@memorialcare.org>
Cc: permissions <permissions@awhonn.org>
Subject: RE: RMC Framework & EBP Guidelines

External EMAIL: This is an email from outside of [REDACTED]

Hi Shari,

Thank you for the email! We are glad you find the materials useful!

For this usage of internally created modules by Shari Kelly for dissemination at Miller Children's Women's Hospital only, you may have permission to use these 2 AWHONN RMC products. The product you develop should reference AWHONN as the source and cite the AWHONN products fully including the following:

Used with permission from AWHONN. To access the AWHONN RMC Framework and Guidelines visit: <https://www.awhonn.org/respectful-maternity-care-implementation-toolkit/>
For all other uses, contact permissions@awhonn.org

This presentation you create should not be posted to any open websites or disseminated to other hospitals. AWHONN does not permit the creation or dissemination of derivative education products.

Please save this email for your records.

Let me know if you have any questions!

Best,

Jill Leonard, MLIS, CLP | Licensing, Copyright & Permissions Manager
Association of Women's Health, Obstetric & Neonatal Nurses (AWHONN)
1800 M Street, NW, Suite 740 South
Washington, DC 20036
[Hide message history](#)

SK

Figure B.1

AWHONN Respectful Maternal Care Framework

Appendix C

IRB – Project Site

[REDACTED] Research Administration – Office of Human Research Protections
 17360 Brookhurst Street, Fountain Valley, CA 92708
 Phone (657) 241-3740 | Fax (657) 241-3746 | [REDACTED]
 Human Subjects Assurance No. FWA00000081

Quality Assurance / Quality Improvement vs. Research Self Determination Form

DATE OF SELF DETERMINATION	5/19/2022	
PROJECT TITLE	Improving Perceptions of Respectful Care Among Black Women	
PROJECT LEADER NAME	Shari Kelly	
REGULATORY CONTACT	Name	Shari Kelly
	Email	[REDACTED]

From HRP SOP #303 – What constitutes a QA/QI project:

Quality Assurance or Quality Improvement Projects (QA/QI): consists of quality improvement activities to implement a practice to improve the quality of patient care, and/or collecting patient or provider data regarding the implementation of the practice for clinical, practical, or administrative purposes to improve or assess internal practices, programs or systems. These initiatives could involve systematic, data-guided activities to improve clinical care, patient safety and health care operations, but they are not designed to contribute to generalizable knowledge. QA/QI initiatives could also involve evaluating and improving existing services and programs or for developing new services and programs.

QA/QI projects may be designed to accomplish one of the following purposes:

- Evaluate the adoption of Evidence-Based Practice guidelines at one or more [REDACTED] facilities (e.g., customer satisfaction surveys)
- Collect patient or provider data regarding the implementation of a practice which served to improve clinical care, for clinical, practical, or administrative purposes
- Implement a practice to improve the quality of clinical care
- Changing clinical systems or processes
- Introduce accepted Best Practice guidelines or procedures to reduce error or improve outcome at one or more [REDACTED]

QA/QI projects do not need to be submitted to HRP or IRB for review.

If you think your proposed activity is a QA/QI project you may use this form to make a self-determination and save it for your files.

1. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

Implementing recommendations from the AWHONN Respectful Maternal Care Evidence-Based Clinical Practice Guideline in the [REDACTED] Pre-and Post-intervention data will be collected to determine the efficacy of the intervention.

QUALITY ASSURANCE / QUALITY IMPROVEMENT VS. RESEARCH SELF DETERMINATION FORM

2. SELF-DETERMINE THE PROJECT IS QA/QI AND DOES NOT CONSTITUTE "RESEARCH" (IF ANY BOX IS CHECKED NO, OR IT IS UNCLEAR, SUBMIT PROJECT TO HRP FOR REVIEW)

INTENT – Is the intent of project to learn about, or improve, an internal [REDACTED] process, program, or MemorialCare clinical practice as part of the [REDACTED] QA program?

Yes No

If the intent is to create information applicable and generalizable to organizations outside [REDACTED], answer 'no'.

SCOPE – Is the scope of the project meant to generate results applicable to a specific MemorialCare process, program, or clinical practice?

Yes No

If the scope is to explore both [REDACTED] and other organizations to create information generalizable to other settings outside [REDACTED], answer 'no'.

PUBLICATION – Are the results of the project intended only to be used internally, or possibly limited to public presentations at conferences, QA journals, or similar outlets where the project is clearly labeled as QA activity?

Yes No

If the intent is to publish the results of the project in a broader fashion to be generalized to other organizations; or, results presented as research, answer 'no'.

If you answered "no" to any of the above, or you are not clear. **STOP.** Your project is likely research and must be submitted to HRP for review.

- Visit the [ServiceNow Research Project Submission Portal support page](#) on the [REDACTED] Intranet for training and guidance materials.

3. SIGNATURE OF PERSON COMPLETING SELF ASSESSMENT

All aspects of the project generated "yes" responses above. Project is self-assessed to be QA/QI and submission to, or review by, ORA HRP is not required.

Shari Kelly		05/19/22
Print Full Name	Signature	Date (mm/dd/yy)

QUESTIONS ABOUT THIS FORM:

- Email [REDACTED] with any questions about this application/form.

Appendix D

Project Site Approval

February 25, 2022

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

This letter is to show that I, **Dr. Susan Herman**, as the Chief Nursing Executive of [REDACTED], give permission to **Sharilyn Kelly** to conduct the project titled *Improving Perceptions of Respectful Maternal Care among Black Women* on the following units: Labor & Delivery Services, Perinatal Special Care Unit and Postpartum Care Unit.

Upon obtaining all necessary clearances from the Nursing Research Council at [REDACTED], and after obtaining the necessary IRB determination/approval, the above-named project lead can:

1. Collect Patient Reported Experience Measures (PREM) by Qualtrics survey administered through the CMQCC Birth Equity Collaborative and distributed by Stanford School of Medicine.
2. Collect the Hospital Consumer Assessment of Healthcare Providers and Systems (HCAHPS) survey responses regarding nurses providing respectful and courteous care.
3. Access and analyze PREM and HCAHPS data to determine project baseline and outcome measures regarding respectful maternal care.
4. Train Perinatal Nursing staff to *Commit to Sit* to engage with and get to know their patients fears and desires regarding their birth experience.
5. Have each staff member commit to provide Respectful Maternal Care by Committing to:
 - a. Patient advocacy
 - b. Provide evidence-based care
 - c. Listening with empathy, not only to respond but to understand
 - d. Treating with dignity and respect
 - e. Shared decision-making

The project lead is responsible for ensuring that all activities related to conducting the project are in compliance with the policies that govern practice, HIPPA, and research and research-related regulations at [REDACTED] and its covered entities.

If you have any questions or concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Dr. Susan Herman, CNE, DNP, RN, NEA-BC, CENP
Chief Nursing Executive, [REDACTED]
Chief Nursing Officer, [REDACTED]

Appendix E

University IRB Approval

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LONG BEACH

OFFICE OF RESEARCH & SPONSORED PROGRAMS

DATE: September 6, 2022

TO: Sharilyn Kelly
FROM: California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board

PROJECT TITLE: [1929397-2] Improving Perceptions of Respectful Maternal Care among Black Women

REFERENCE #: 22-271

SUBMISSION TYPE: New Project

REVIEW TYPE: Expedited Review

ACTION: APPROVED

APPROVAL DATE: September 6, 2022

EXPIRATION DATE: September 6, 2023

This is to advise you that the Institutional Review Board for the Protection of Human Subjects (IRB) of California State University, Long Beach, has reviewed your protocol application.

Approval is effective beginning September 6, 2022 and will expire September 6, 2023. Approval is conditional upon your willingness to carry out your continuing responsibilities under University policy. This project must adhere to the following conditions:

1. You must clearly indicate in the header or footer of each page of your approved Informed Consent Form and recruitment material as follows: **"Approved from September 6, 2022 to September 6, 2023 by the CSULB IRB."**
2. **If you need to make changes/revision to this approved project, you must submit a Request for Amendment to an Approved Protocol in addition to any documents affected by the requested change. Submit these documents as a subsequent package to this approved project via IRBNet. You are not allowed to implement any changes to your research activities prior to obtaining final approval of you requested amendment from the CSULB IRB.**
3. You are required to inform the Director of Research Integrity and Compliance, Office of Research & Sponsored Programs, via email at ORED-Compliance@csulb.edu within twenty-four hours of any adverse event in the conduct of research involving human subjects. The report shall include the nature of the adverse event, the names of the persons affected, the extent of the injury or breach of confidentiality or data security, if any, and any other information material to the situation.
4. Maintain your research records as detailed in the protocol.
5. If you would like to continue this research after this one-year period, please submit a Annual Check in form, updated IRB Application and all relevant project documents to the CSULB IRB one month prior to your project expiration date of September 6, 2023.

Should you have any questions about the conduct of your research under this protocol, particularly about providing informed consent and unexpected contingencies, please do not hesitate to contact the IRB Office via email, IRB@csulb.edu, or call (562) 985-8147. Please specify your project title and reference number in all correspondence with this committee. We wish you the best of success in your research.

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board's records.

1250 Bellflower Blvd., Long Beach, CA 90840
Ph. (562) 985-8147 Fax. (562) 985-8665

Appendix F

University IRB Revision Approval

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LONG BEACH

OFFICE OF RESEARCH & ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

DATE: March 6, 2023

TO: Sharilyn Kelly
FROM: California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board

PROJECT TITLE: [1929397-3] Improving Perceptions of Respectful Maternal Care among Black Women

REFERENCE #: 22-271

SUBMISSION TYPE: Revision

REVIEW TYPE: Administrative Review

ACTION: APPROVED

APPROVAL DATE: March 6, 2023

EXPIRATION DATE: September 6, 2023

This is to advise you that the Institutional Review Board for the Protection of Human Subjects (IRB) of California State University, Long Beach, has reviewed your protocol amendment application.

Your protocol amendment to Add patient responses to survey question from the Project site's Hospital Consumer Assessment of Healthcare Providers and Systems (HCAHPS) monthly report "How often did nurses treat you with courtesy and respect." is approved by Administrative Review.

Approval is effective beginning March 6, 2023 and will expire September 6, 2023. Approval is conditional upon your willingness to carry out your continuing responsibilities under University policy. This project must adhere to the following conditions:

1. You must clearly indicate in the header or footer of each page of your approved Informed Consent Form and recruitment material as follows: **"Approved from March 6, 2023 to September 6, 2023 by the CSULB IRB."**
2. If you need to make changes/revision to this approved project, you must submit a Request for Amendment to an Approved Protocol in addition to any documents affected by the requested change. Submit these documents as a subsequent package to this approved project via IRBNet. You are not allowed to implement any changes to your research activities prior to obtaining final approval of you requested amendment from the CSULB IRB.
3. You are required to inform the Director of Research Integrity and Compliance, Office of Research & Sponsored Programs, via email at ORSPCompliance@csulb.edu within twenty-four hours of any adverse event in the conduct of research involving human subjects. The report shall include the nature of the adverse event, the names of the persons affected, the extent of the injury or breach of confidentiality or data security, if any, and any other information material to the situation.

4. Maintain your research records as detailed in the protocol.
5. If you would like to continue this research after this one-year period, please submit a Continuing Review application, updated IRB Application and all relevant project documents to the CSULB IRB one month prior to your project expiration date of September 6, 2023.

Should you have any questions about the conduct of your research under this protocol, particularly about providing informed consent and unexpected contingencies, please do not hesitate to contact the IRB Office via email, IRB@csulb.edu, or call (562) 985-8147. Please specify your project title and reference number in all correspondence with this committee. We wish you the best of success in your research.

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board's records.

1250 Bellflower Blvd., Long Beach, CA 90840
Ph. (562) 985-8147 Fax. (562) 985-8665

Appendix G

Permission to use PREM Data

From: Terri Deeds <tdeeds@stanford.edu>
Sent: Wednesday, June 15, 2022 11:29 AM
To: Sharilyn Kelly <[REDACTED]>
Subject: RE: CMQCC Birth Equity PREM report

Leslie Ann Kowalski has authorized you to use your PREM data from CMQCC's perspective. You will undoubtedly work out permission from [REDACTED] to allow you to use their data. Thank you for asking and good luck with your project.

Terri Deeds (she/her), MSN, RN, NE-BC, C-ONQS
Clinical Lead, CMQCC

Stanford University School of Medicine
Mail: tdeeds@stanford.edu
MDC Support: datacenter@cmqcc.org

CMQCC

Appendix H

Informed Consent

Notice of Informed Consent

Project Title: Respectful Maternal Care

Investigator(s): Sharilyn L. Kelly, MSN/MSHA, RN, NE-BC, C-ONOS, RNC-OB

Project Contact: [REDACTED]

California State University, Long Beach (CSULB)

Office of Research and Economic Development, CSULB: 1250 Bellflower Blvd., Long Beach, CA 90840

You are being asked to participate in a research study. The participants should be 18 years or older. The purpose of this study is to determine patients' perceptions of respectful maternal care. If you decide to participate you will be asked to respond to survey questions which are all for research purposes. You may skip any of the experience questions but not the demographic questions as they are essential to this study. The total time of your participation is expected to last five minutes. The risks to participating in this study include potential distress if recalling a traumatic birth, obstetric racism or abuse, or perinatal loss during this experience. The investigator will make every attempt to reduce these risks by providing links to resources at the bottom of this page to address any distress you may have by recalling your birth experience. You may not directly benefit from participating in this study. However, the results of this study may benefit other birthing women by improving care at MemorialCare Miller Children's & Women's Hospital Long Beach as well as across the state of California. Any information collected from you in this study will be stored in a secure location and will not be shared with anyone who does not have appropriate provisions to access the information.

If you have questions about this specific study, you may contact me at skelly@memorialcare.org or my Faculty Advisor, Melissa Dyo at Melissa.Dyo@CSULB.edu. You may contact the Office of Research and Sponsored Programs at ORED-Compliance@csulb.edu, or calling (562) 985-8147, if you have questions about your rights as a research participant.

Selecting "I consent, begin the study" below means that all information about the study has been explained to you, the investigator has answered any questions you have about the study and that you voluntarily agree to participate.

Postpartum support resources:

<http://postpartum.net/>

<http://maternalmentalhealthnow.org/>

<http://womenshealth.gov/mental-health>

<http://newmomhealth.com/>

1-833-9-HELP4MOMS (1-833-943-5746)

Appendix I

Patient Reported Experience Measure (PREM) Survey

Your feedback is important to us, it will help us to improve how we care for mothers and birthing people at (Project Facility). Your responses will be totally anonymous with the results of this survey used for our internal quality improvement only. Please take 5 minutes and tell us about your experience giving birth.

Thank you.

Thinking about the way you were treated during your hospital birthing experience, how often did:

Doctors, nurses or other staff at the hospital asked my permission before carrying out procedures and examinations.

Always Most of the time About half the time Sometimes Never

The doctors, nurses, and midwives listened to and respected my wishes.

Always Most of the time About half the time Sometimes Never

When the health care team could not meet my wishes, they explained why.

Always Most of the time About half the time Sometimes Never

I trusted my doctors, nurses and other staff at the hospital to take the best care of me.

Always Most of the time About half the time Sometimes Never

Thinking about your hospital birthing experience, please indicate your agreement with the following statements:

The staff made me feel cared for as an individual.

Strongly agree Somewhat agree Neither agree nor disagree Somewhat disagree Strongly disagree

The healthcare team helped create a comfortable, caring environment.

Strongly agree Somewhat agree Neither agree nor disagree Somewhat disagree Strongly disagree

The healthcare team supported my cultural or family traditions.

Strongly agree Somewhat agree Neither agree nor disagree Somewhat disagree Strongly disagree

The staff was compassionate and treated me with kindness.

Strongly agree Somewhat agree Neither agree nor disagree Somewhat disagree Strongly disagree

Overall, during my labor and birth, I felt my personal preferences were respected.

Strongly agree Somewhat agree Neither agree nor disagree Somewhat disagree Strongly disagree

I was treated differently based on my race/ethnicity during my hospital birthing experience.

Strongly agree Somewhat agree Neither agree nor disagree Somewhat disagree Strongly disagree

I was treated differently based on my insurance status during my hospital birthing experience.

Strongly agree Somewhat agree Neither agree nor disagree Somewhat disagree Strongly disagree

I was treated differently based on my sexual orientation or gender identify during my hospital birthing experience.

Strongly agree Somewhat agree Neither agree nor disagree Somewhat disagree Strongly disagree

We value your opinion, If you have comments about your birthing experience you would like to share with us, please add it below:

Please indicate how you identify yourself (race/ethnicity)

Asian Black Hispanic White Other Decline to state

Was this your first birth?

Yes No

What is your age?

Under 20 years old 20 -24 25-30 31-34 35-40 Over 40

Stanforduniversity.qualtrics.com

Appendix J

Invitation to Participate

The California Maternal Quality Care Collaborative is a large group of California Hospitals working together to improve maternity care for families.

Hospital Long Beach

We invite you to complete a short survey about your childbirth experience. Your anonymous responses will help improve maternity care at [redacted] as well as across the state.

**Your voice matters.
Tu voz es importante.**

Te invitamos a completar una breve encuesta sobre tu experiencia de parto. Las anonimas respuestas ayudarán a mejorar la atención de maternidad en [redacted] así como en todo el estado.

Tell us about your birth experience by scanning this code!
¡Cuéntanos sobre tu experiencia de parto escaneando este código!

Appendix K

HCAHPS Survey Question

HCAHPS Survey

SURVEY INSTRUCTIONS

- ◆ You should only fill out this survey if you were the patient during the hospital stay named in the cover letter. Do not fill out this survey if you were not the patient.
- ◆ Answer all the questions by checking the box to the left of your answer.
- ◆ You are sometimes told to skip over some questions in this survey. When this happens you will see an arrow with a note that tells you what question to answer next, like this:
 - Yes
 - No → **If No, Go to Question 1**

You may notice a number on the survey. This number is used to let us know if you returned your survey so we don't have to send you reminders.

Please note: Questions 1-29 in this survey are part of a national initiative to measure the quality of care in hospitals. OMB #0938-0981 (Expires September 30, 2024)

Please answer the questions in this survey about your stay at the hospital named on the cover letter. Do not include any other hospital stays in your answers.

YOUR CARE FROM NURSES

1. During this hospital stay, how often did nurses treat you with courtesy and respect?
 - 1 Never
 - 2 Sometimes
 - 3 Usually
 - 4 Always

<https://www.hcahpsonline.org> Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services, Baltimore, MD.

February, 25, 2023

Appendix L

Project Timeline

Timeline: Month	June22	July	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan23
Present project to the BCC Leadership team and Birth Equity Team for endorsement								
Collect baseline data: PREM and HCAHPS survey responses 2nd ^o CY22	Start March 2022							
Obtain facility & school IRB approvals								
Adapt AWHONN RMC education materials and tools								
Online training assigned to RNs via YouLearn LMS		July 17						
Launch RMC Commitment intervention throughout the BCC.								
Selection, orientation, and training of RMC champions								
RMC champions have 1:1 with RNs to secure commitment								
Collect post-intervention data: PREM and HCAPHS survey results				Aug Data	Sept Data	Oct Data	Nov Data	Dec Data

Appendix M

Respectful Maternal Care Commitment Form

Part of providing **Respectful Maternity Care** is holding myself accountable even when it's uncomfortable, (especially when it's uncomfortable). Our accountability starts here, and it starts now.

Name: _____ Department: _____

Date attended Learning: _____

As a [REDACTED] BirthCare Center RN I am committed to:

- ✓ I commit to sit with my patient and learn their goals for perinatal care and discuss my personal commitment to RMC
- ✓ I am willing to be uncomfortable and engage in constructive conversation about incivility, inequality, and racism.
- ✓ I will embrace conflict as an opportunity for growth.
- ✓ I will notice who is the center of attention and who is the center of power.
- ✓ When I have done or said something that offends someone, I will attend to the consequences of my actions rather than defend my intentions.
- ✓ I will *avoid* normalizing disrespect by:
 - Making comments such as "Birth plans lead to C/S"
 - Making fun of a newborn's name
 - Minimizing trauma by saying "at least the baby is ok"

"ersonal commitment (choose at least one as your focus)

- I will Commit to providing evidence-based care.
- I will Commit to shared decision-making.
- I will Commit to advocating for all patients.
- I will Commit to listening with empathy, not only to respond but to understand.
- I will Commit to treating everyone with dignity and respect.

Would you like an accountability check-in two months from now? Yes No

Signed: _____

Date _____

Appendix N

Respectful Maternity Care (RMC) Champion Role

Performance Improvement Need

The performance improvement opportunity was identified through our Birth Equity Collaborative with CMQCC. During our analysis of our Patient Reported Experience Measures (PREM), we noted the need to refresh our nursing philosophy to ensure we provide respectful maternal care by committing to patient advocacy, providing evidence-based care, listening with empathy, not only to respond but to understand, shared decision-making, and treating all patients and families with dignity and respect.

Primary Role Responsibilities

A champion believes in, supports, and fights for a cause. A Respectful Maternity Care (RMC) champion is a member of the [BirthCare](#) Center team that promotes respectful maternity care for every patient, every interaction, every time.

RMC champion role description/qualifications:

- Leads by example, promoting respectful, equitable care for mothers and newborns (CUPA-HR, 2020).
- Identifies opportunities for improvement in the respective work area and each role (CUPA-HR, 2020).
- Collaborative learner who is open to new ideas and constructive feedback and does not see participation as a burden (Center for Urban Education, 2020).
- Friendly skeptic who raises questions and provides critique that will ultimately make the team more effective (Center for Urban Education, 2020).
- Acts as an information resource for colleagues and helps disseminate RMC education as needed (Global Internships, 2020).
- Attends and participates in RMC Champion meetings.
- Collects and analyzes data as described below:

Empirical Outcomes (to be completed by champion once champion role implemented)

Initial metrics will focus on the number of staff completing the commitment education module and committing to respectful maternal care. The RMC champions will develop/identify a survey to measure nurse satisfaction related to meaningful and purposeful work after RMC has been fully implemented. The RMC champions will review and analyze the PREM data to detect improvement in the identified gaps after ≥85% of the BCC staff have completed their RMC commitment.

Additional Element Wording and Requirements: Additional Element Wording and Requirements: Serve as a “champion” in a defined practice-oriented role driven by a performance improvement need to improve outcomes. The champion role must be approved by the Nurse Executive Council.

- Submit the approved, defined unit criteria for your role.
- Submit a written description of your role.
- Submit an evaluation of the impact/outcome of your champion role.
- Submit a letter from the manager validating your role.

References

- Center for Urban Education. (2020). Guide for composing a campus racial equity team. [Bosler, School of Education, University of Southern California](#). https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5eb5c03682a92c5f96da4fc8/t/5f3a19eccedac416422701b6/1597643247590/2018+Equity+Team+Formation+Guide_Summer2020.pdf
- CUPA-HR. (2020). Become a better champion for DEI by focusing on these three areas. <https://www.cupahr.org/blog/become-a-better-champion-for-dei-by-focusing-on-these-three-areas/>
- Global Internships. (2020). How to champion diversity in the workplace (and how it can benefit your business). <https://www.globalinternships.com/post/how-to-champion-diversity-in-the-workplace-and-how-it-can-benefit-your-business>

Step 2 of AWHONN RMC Toolkit

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Appendix O

Process Measures

Figure O.1

Cumulative RMC Module Completion Rates

Figure O.2

Commit to Sit Compliance Percentage per week

Appendix P

Outcome Measures

Figure P.1

HCAHPS Baseline and Post-Intervention Data Results

Figure P.2*PREM Baseline and Post-Intervention Data Results*